

Conference Feedback Report: ISSCP 2024

Topic	Excellent (%)	Very good (%)	Good (%)	Average (%)	Below average (%)	Did not attend the lecture (%)
Workshops: After participating in the workshop, my knowledge in the field is	23	32	41	4	-	-
Workshops: After participating in the workshop, I feel that the usefulness of the knowledge acquired in terms of clinical application is	28	33	34	5	-	-
Ethnic differences in pharmacogenomic variant distribution: possible impacts on the population specific outcomes in cardiology and oncology-Dr. Ambili Sivadas	34	40	21	4	1	-
Challenges and possible solutions in communicating pharmacogenomic results to clinicians and end users - Experiences from India- Dr. Vinod Scaria	35	40	21	3	1	-
The journey to clinical pharmacogenomics implementation in Qatar-Dr. Ayah ziyada	21	39	28	10	2	-
Challenges in using medication in cardiology and possible solutions-Utility of Pharmacogenomics- Dr. Hisham Ahamed	42	32	21	3	2	-
Precision Cardiology: Harnessing pharmacogenomics for enhanced efficacy and patient safety with anti-platelet therapy- Dr. Priyadharsini Rajendran	27	41	23	9	-	-
Circulating microRNA as a biomarker for platelet reactivity: a new tool to tailor antithrombotic therapy- Prof. Pierre Fontana	31	37	24	5	-	3
Implementation of pharmacogenetic testing for oral anticoagulant dosing in a tertiary care hospital setting in Western India- Dr. Sheetal K	27	41	25	5	1	1
Physiologically based pharmacokinetic modelling concepts and its implications in personalized medicine practice in cardiology. Case studies on drug - drug interactions- Dr. Youssef Daali	34	37	20	7	1	1
Population structure differences: opportunities for a personalized dosing using population modelling -case studies- Dr. Surulivelrajan M	29	34	27	7	-	3
Talk: Clinical implications of Pharmacogenomics in oncology practice-case study on immune checkpoint inhibitors- Dr. Nikhil Krishna Haridas	35	38	21	3	1	2
Debate: Are we there yet, or it is just the beginning - implementation of pharmacogenomics in oncology clinical cure? Dr.Rekha and Dr. Gerard M Raj	31	30	29	6	-	4
Talk: Pharmacogenomics in oncology: applications in practice and opportunities for research- Dr. Prashant Ganesan	35	32	27	4	-	2
Talk: Current CPIC guidelines in oncology and pharmacogenomic- Dr. Uppugunduri S Chakradhara Rao	38	34	21	4	1	2
Talk: Incorporation of pharmacogenetic information into population	34	37	23	5	1	-

models - case study from oncology- Dr. Khalil Ben Hassine						
Talk: Pharmacogenomics testing in oncology -Amrita s' experience- Dr Sachin David	39	31	26	4	-	-
Panel Discussion: Tools (e.g. Pharmacogenomics, Pharmacometrics, TDM) with implications of bringing in precision for optimized therapy in oncology- Dr. Wesley, Dr. Khalil BH, Dr. Folefac and Dr Sachin David	45	32	19	4	-	-
Talk: Precision Health Pharmacogenomics Research and Clinical Implementation in Oncology. Current Status and Future Challenges specific emphasis on biological molecules- Dr. Folefac Aminkeng	43	32	20	4	1	-
Talk: How to implement pharmacogenomic testing service in a hospital setting? experience from a pediatric oncology setting in Egypt- Dr. Mohamed Nagy	29	40	21	6	2	2
Talk: Perspectives of oncologist, clinical pharmacologist, test providers, Basic Researcher on pharmacogenomic testing in oncology- Dr. Nikhil, Dr. G. Lakshmi and Dr. Shana S	35	32	24	7	-	2
Talk: Germline genetic testing in hematological malignancies- scope for contribution- Dr. Neeraj Sidharthan	37	30	24	5	-	4
Overall: Improvement of your understanding	26	41	29	3	1	-
Overall: Improvement of your domain expertise	21	34	39	5	1	-
Overall: Perceived usefulness of pharmacogenomics in the future	43	29	25	4	-	-